

doi:10.5281/zenodo.15068543

Perception and Attitude of Career Mothers on Exclusive Breastfeeding in Selected Public Organisations in Oyo State, Nigeria

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ABSTRACT

This paper reported the outcome of a study which investigated the perception and attitude of working career mothers on exclusive breastfeeding in two public organisations, University of Ibadan and University College Hospital, in Oyo State, Nigeria. Literature is rich on breastfeeding newly born babies/infants among women of child-bearing age in Nigeria. However, there is insufficiently literature documentation on career mother's believe in exclusive breastfeeding in the study's selected two public organisations. The descriptive survey design was adopted. The population of the study comprised career mothers employed in the University of Ibadan and the University College Hospital (UCH) totalling 3,000 while the sample size was 176 career women selected through snowballing sample size determination formula: $n = N/(1+Ne2)$. Perception and Attitude of Career Mothers on Exclusive Breastfeeding Questionnaire ($r=77$) was used to obtain data. Data collected were analysed using frequency count, percentages, mean and standard deviation while the only hypotheses was tested through Pearson product moment correlation coefficient. Findings showed that the respondents (career mothers) had a positive perception of exclusive breastfeeding and its inherent benefits and they also had positive attitude towards exclusive breastfeeding practice. Lastly, the relationship between the perception and attitude of career mother had significant impact on exclusive breastfeeding practice ($r=.687$, $n=176$, $p (.001) <.05$). The paper recommended strategies for improving the practice of exclusive breastfeeding among working career mothers in public and private organisations in Nigeria.

Keywords: Perception, Attitude, Exclusive Breastfeeding, University of Ibadan, University College Hospital

INTRODUCTION

Breastfeeding is an old practice and unique biological method of feeding newly born babies/infants with mothers' breast milk from birth to virtual two years and sometimes above depending on cultural, religious and personal beliefs for healthy growth and development of the infants and optimal health of the mothers. Universally, the very first stage of improving child's survival is as a consequence of breastfeeding; hence breast milk as a food is importantly beneficial for the growth of an infant. It enriches the physical, mental, and social growth of a child. Breast milk contains many nutritional values like antibodies which enhance the immunity of a child, prevents child mortality and morbidity.

Breast milk has an enormous impact on the health of infants, most especially those who weighed less at birth. It has been discovered that breast milk is far more nutritious than processed milk. Aside from the benefits of breast milk on an infant, breastfeeding creates an inevitable bond between a mother and her child (Heckman, 2011).

Oche, Umar and Ahmed (2011) asserted that for almost all infants, breastfeeding remains the simplest, healthiest and least expensive feeding method that fulfils the infant needs. Mother's milk has antibodies which are not present in infant formula (Sholeye, Abosede, & Salako, 2015). These antibodies are what protect the body and boost the immune system of newly born babies/infants to enable them fight diseases such as respiratory tract disease, skin infection, diarrhea, among others (Jones, 2013).

The human milk in the right proportion also helps in robust and all round development of infant (Tiwari, Tyndall, Kamai, & Chanchangi, 2018). To reduce infant morbidity and mortality arising from infant-related diseases, scholars and personnel in health organisations have recommended exclusive breastfeeding (EBF) defined as an infant's consumption of mothers' milk with no supplementation of any type (no water, no juice, no non-human milk, and no foods) except for vitamins, minerals, and medications until six months" (World Health Organisation, 2009). Similarly, UNICEF (2010) defined exclusive breastfeeding as giving baby breast milk only and nothing else, not even sips of water except for medicines prescribed by the doctor or nurse for the first six months of life.

During the first two months of life, infants who are not breastfed are nearly six times more likely to die from infectious diseases than infants who are breastfed; between 2 and 3 months, non-breastfed infants are 4 times more likely to die compared to breastfed infants (Dana, Price, Simon, & Schuster, 1987). The World Health Organisation [WHO] (2020) corroborated this view that infants who are not fed with breast milk at the first 60 days of their birth are likely to die from infection than those who are breastfed. In essence, breastfeeding is the nursing of young ones with the mother's breast milk as soon as they are born, starting from the very first hour of a baby's birth (Medical Definition of Breastfeeding, 2022).

Even though the benefits of exclusive breast feeding have been well-documented in literature, there exist some barriers to exclusive breastfeeding also documented in literature. For example, a study conducted by Rockville (2012) in the USA on perception of mothers on exclusive breastfeeding reported the inconveniences of exclusive breast feeding as 45% of the respondents indicated that they had to give up many habits and change their lifestyle. Similarly, the following barriers were reported in literature: risks of poor-quality breast milk (Aboubacar, 2017; Agani et al., 2017), perceived low breastfeeding efficacy (including low breast milk supply) (Klemm, Burns, & Amundson, 2012), inadequate counseling on exclusive breast-feeding practices in a ; poor urban setting (Alutu & Orubu, 2006; Aluko & Sunday, 2012; & Ochola, Labadarios, & Nduati, 2013); and breastfeeding's influence on maternal body image (Agunbaide, & Ogunleye, 2012; & Alzaheb, 2017).

The documented barriers to exclusive breastfeeding prompted this study to investigate the perception and attitude of career women in two selected public organisations - University of Ibadan and University College Hospital- both located in Ibadan North Local Government Area in Oyo State, Nigeria.

Statement of the Problem

The advocacy for exclusive breastfeeding from nursing mothers to their newly born babies/infants has been preached and promoted globally including Nigeria irrespective of women age, status, and educational background. It is well-documented in literature that women of child-bearing age in Nigeria, irrespective of their career, believe in breastfeeding newly born babies/infants. However, what has not been sufficiently documented is if career mothers believe in exclusive breastfeeding. In other words, not much information or research evidence exists on the perception and attitude of career mothers working in government establishments on exclusive breastfeeding. This is because career mothers resume work after the mandatory three-month maternity leave. Their resumption at work may not give them the opportunity to practice exclusive breastfeeding. If they do not sufficiently practice exclusive breastfeeding, the consequences on the newly born babies/infants are well-known in literature. Therefore, there is the need to find out the perception and attitude of career mothers to exclusive breastfeeding with a view of developing mechanisms for motivating them to adequately practice exclusive breastfeeding since studies have shown that newly born babies/infants who are

not fed exclusively from or with breast milk at the first 60 days of their birth are likely to die from infection than those who are breastfed.

Objectives of the Study and Hypothesis

Two specific objectives were raised for the study while one hypothesis was tested. The objectives were, to:

- i. Determine the perception of career mothers on exclusive breastfeeding in the two public organisations selected for the study, and
- ii. Ascertain the attitude of career mother on exclusive breastfeeding practice in the two public organisations.

The hypothesis raised was structured to find out if there was a significant relationship or not between the attitude of career mothers to exclusive breastfeeding and the practice of exclusive breastfeeding.

The Theoretical Framework

The theoretical framework of the study is anchored on the Health Belief Model (HBM). This model was propounded by Rosentock in 1974. This study hinged on the Health Belief Model (HBM), on the premise that successful breastfeeding practice is largely dependent on the target audience's knowledge of the benefits to be derived if adopted and the risks involved. The Health Belief Model (HBM) was developed as a theory to guide design intervention and prevention programs. Subsequently, it was extended by Leventhal, Rosenstock, and Becker in 1966 to explain differing reactions to symptoms and to explain variations in adherence to treatment.

Mojaye (2008) states that the HBM is based on the understanding that a person will take a health-related action if that person feels a negative health condition can be avoided and is convinced that taking the recommended action would yield positive results. Since health behaviours are influenced by a person's desire to avoid illness (perceived susceptibility) or to get well, and by their confidence that the recommended action will achieve this, it is assumed that by understanding the benefits of exclusive breastfeeding (perceived benefits) and having a good knowledge of the danger of not completing the six months exclusive breastfeeding (perceived severity), mothers will have the confidence to overcome the challenges and exclusively breastfeed their babies for six months.

According to Ogwezzy-Ndisika (2012), access to information creates awareness which affects perception and in turn leads to acceptance. Sensitizing and educating mothers on the advantages of exclusive breastfeeding; and providing adequate information on how to deal with the challenges will help mothers adopt the desired their behaviour. Certain factors such as cultural beliefs and norms as perceived by the individual may serve as barriers to the desired behaviour (perceived barriers). For instance, mothers might fail to breast-feed their infants for fear of the breast-milk not being adequate for the infants' nutrition. External factors also influence the desired behaviour, serving as cues to action. In the case of exclusive breastfeeding, information from health professionals, radio and television as well support and encouragement from family members and relatives may influence mother to exclusively breastfeed their babies.

METHODOLOGY

The research design adopted by the study was the descriptive survey design which is a scientific method of observing and describing the behaviour of a subject without influencing it in any way. This design was considered appropriate because it allowed the investigation of relationships among variables. The career mothers were considered as the independent variable which encompasses attitude, perception and knowledge of career mothers which cannot be manipulated. The population of the study comprised career mothers employed in the University of Ibadan and the University College Hospital (UCH) totalling 3,000. The eligibility criteria of inclusion of the respondents in the study were: must be a mother, must be able to communicate (read, write and speak) in English Language, and must willingly consent to participate in the study. The sample size was 176 career women selected through snowballing sample size determination formula: $n = N/(1+Ne^2)$ where n is sample size; N is population size; e is error margin; and $n = 3000 / (1 + 3000 * .052) = 3000 / 8.8 = 176$ career mothers. A modified a 4-point Likert scale (.77) was used to obtain data. Data collected were analysed using frequency count, percentages, mean and standard deviation. The only hypotheses stated was tested at 0.05 level of significance through Pearson product moment correlation coefficient.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

The results on the demographic characteristics of the respondents showed that majority of the respondents falls within the 26-35 years age range (32.4%), followed by the 18-25 years group (23.9%), indicating a trend of young to middle-aged mothers in the workforce. Most mothers are married (51.7%). In terms of education, a substantial majority hold at least a B.Sc./HND (60.8%), reflecting the high educational attainment of career mothers in the area, with smaller percentages having lower or higher qualifications. The job status data showed that most mothers are employed in senior cadre positions (69.3%), suggesting a higher level of professional achievement and responsibility. Majority of the respondents have between 1-3 children (82.4%). Work experience is fairly evenly split, with 52.3% having 1-10 years of experience and 47.7% with 11 years or more. The motherhood profile revealed that 52.8% of mothers are currently pregnant and 39.2% are breastfeeding. Results of the research questions are presented below. Research question one was raised to determine the perception of career mothers on exclusive breastfeeding in the two public organisations selected for the study. The result is presented in table 1.

Table 1: Perception of career mothers about benefits of exclusive breastfeeding practices

S/N	Perception of career mothers about the benefit of exclusive breastfeeding practice	SD	D	A	SA	\bar{x}	S.D.
1.	Exclusive breastfeeding prevents rapid physical growth in babies.	104 59.1%	37 21.0%	21 11.9%	14 8.0%	1.69	0.968
2.	Exclusive breastfeeding has helped to prevent illnesses from my baby.	13 7.4%	18 10.2%	37 21.0%	108 61.4%	3.36	0.940
3.	Exclusive breastfeeding helped me with child spacing.	10 5.7%	20 11.4%	53 30.1%	93 52.8%	3.30	0.885
4.	Exclusive breastfeeding has helped to enhance mother child bonding.	17 9.7%	17 9.7%	51 29.0%	91 51.7%	3.23	0.977
5.	Exclusive breastfeeding helps to ensure regular feeding of my baby.	17 9.7%	19 10.8%	61 34.7%	79 44.9%	3.15	0.963
Weighted Mean =2.95							

Table 1 explored the perception of career mothers regarding the benefits of exclusive breastfeeding. Majority of mothers recognise its positive health and relational impacts, with 61.4% strongly agreeing that exclusive breastfeeding prevents illnesses in their babies and 52.8% agreeing that it aids in child spacing. Additionally, 51.7% strongly agree that it enhances mother-child bonding, reflecting its emotional and relational value. The perception of exclusive breastfeeding as a means to ensure regular feeding is also supported, with 44.9% strongly agreeing. These revealed that career mothers largely appreciate the physical, emotional, and practical benefits of exclusive breastfeeding. A significant majority (59.1%) strongly disagree with the notion that exclusive breastfeeding prevents rapid physical growth in babies, suggesting that this belief does not align with their experiences. With a weighted mean of 2.95, the data highlights an overall positive perception of exclusive breastfeeding among career mothers.

Result further indicated that respondents strongly agreed that the level of perception of career mothers towards exclusive breastfeeding practice commendable while some strongly disagreed. The result on the perception of career mothers about benefits of exclusive breastfeeding practices revealed that majority of the mothers indicated that EBF protect the baby against diarrheal diseases. Others indicated that breast feeding will make the breast sag while others mentioned time consuming and rejection of other feed. The above is in line with the study conducted by Eeia, Michele, Patrick, & Pauline, (2015) in Bangalore province in India. In contrast to the above, Petit (2012) view was that EBF is good and had no complication both for mothers and baby. This calls for proper information dissemination to mothers during ante-natal clinic to clear these misconceptions. Perceptions of vulnerability in the breastfeeding process have a significant relationship with breastfeeding intentions. In this study, most of the respondents have a perception of vulnerability tends to the mother.

This perception of vulnerability if not breastfeeding the baby can be manifested in the form of actions to prevent, reduce, or control several things that are vulnerable to be faced when breastfeeding later. Preventive action against disease is believed to start from a person’s perception of vulnerability and perception of benefit (Conner, 2010). The problem of vulnerability in the breastfeeding process usually arises from the mother, baby, and lack of support from health workers. Especially for mothers who are breastfeeding for the first time, they tend to have low self-efficacy and breastfeeding knowledge (Leurer, Petrucka, Msafiri, 2019).

The result on perception of mother on exclusive breastfeeding revealed that majority of the mothers indicated that EBF protect the baby against diarrheal diseases. Others indicated that breast feeding will make the breast sag while others mentioned time consuming and rejection of other feed. In contrast to the above, the view of Akinremi and Samuel (2015) was that EBF is good and had no complication both for mothers and baby. This calls for proper information dissemination to mothers during Ante Natal Clinic to clear these misconceptions.

Research question two was raised to ascertain the attitude of career mother on exclusive breastfeeding practice in the two public organisations. The result is presented in table 2.

Table 2: Attitude of career mothers towards exclusive breastfeeding practice

S/N	Attitude of career mothers towards exclusive breast-feeding practice	SD	D	A	SA	\bar{x}	S.D.
1.	I don’t feel comfortable breast feeding my infant in the public.	24 13.6%	25 14.2%	42 23.9%	85 48.3%	3.07	1.083
2.	I like exclusive breastfeeding because it also a way of bonding me to my infant.	23 13.1%	15 8.5%	50 28.4%	88 50.0%	3.15	1.044
3.	I don’t like exclusive breast feeding because it causes breast sagging.	82 46.6%	43 24.4%	29 16.5%	22 12.5%	1.95	1.065
4.	I like exclusive breast feeding because it makes my infant look healthier.	17 9.7%	22 12.5%	42 23.9%	95 54.0%	3.22	1.004
5.	I don’t like exclusive breast feeding because my husband feels left out.	99 56.3%	41 23.3%	17 9.7%	19 10.8%	1.75	1.017
6.	I like exclusive breast feeding because it is cheaper.	11 6.3%	21 11.9%	33 18.8%	111 63.1%	3.39	0.925
Weighted Mean =2.75							

Table 2 assesses the attitudes of career mothers in Ibadan North Local Government Area towards exclusive breastfeeding. The results indicated a generally positive attitude towards exclusive breastfeeding, with a majority of respondents strongly agreeing with statements that highlight the benefits of breastfeeding. 50.0% strongly agree that exclusive breastfeeding helps bond them with their infants, and 54.0% strongly agree that it makes their infants look healthier. Furthermore, 63.1% strongly agree that exclusive breastfeeding is cheaper, suggesting that cost-effectiveness is a significant factor in their preference for this practice.

However, the responses also revealed some concerns; 46.6% strongly disagree with the idea of breastfeeding causing breast sagging, and 56.3% strongly disagree that exclusive breastfeeding makes their husbands feel left out, showing that personal and relational factors might influence their attitudes towards breastfeeding. Despite the positive responses to the health and bonding benefits of exclusive breastfeeding, the weighted mean of 2.75 indicated a positive attitude towards the practice. Additionally, the concern about breast sagging, despite being less pronounced, could still influence some mothers' willingness to fully embrace exclusive breastfeeding.

Results in table 2 indicated that over three-quarters of the respondents strongly agreed that they intended to breastfeed their babies. Respondents also strongly agreed that they would advise other mothers to breastfeed their babies, and that breastfeeding was important for the health and wellbeing of the baby. In terms of work, more than two-thirds of the respondents felt that their work did not have to interfere with breastfeeding schedules, and that they would breastfeed while at work during a break in a designated area. This is in line with Wojcicki et al. (2010) investigated maternal attitudes towards breastfeeding in San Francisco, California, by interviewing mothers who recently delivered a healthy newborn.

The main findings of the study showed that those participants who were using instant formula were more likely to have a negative attitude towards breastfeeding. Elements that promoted the negative attitude were embarrassment of breastfeeding in public, physical concerns, uncomfortable feelings and negative influence from family/friends. Stuebe & Bonuck (2011) also found comfort with breastfeeding in social environments and knowledge about the benefits of breastfeeding as factors related to the intension of exclusively breastfeeding practice.

The authors suggested that strong reinforced messages about the health benefits of breastfeeding and strategies for encouraging breastfeeding in social environments should increase the duration and the exclusivity. In another study, Idris et al. (2012) found that Asian women, who are not well informed about breastfeeding advantages or who previously have breastfed for a short period tend to exclusively breastfeed shorter than the recommendations. Also Asian women who work tend to have a shorter duration of exclusive breastfeeding. Increasing age and parity were associated with increasingly negative attitudes toward breastfeeding among urban nursing women in this study. This suggests that the different elements of each individual's HBM, such as age and number of live births, moderate the mother's decision to engage in exclusive breastfeeding, despite knowledge of its benefits and positive attitudes to its outcomes.

Basically, positive maternal attitudes toward breastfeeding are associated with continuing to breastfeed longer and having a greater chance of successful breastfeeding. Besides, mothers with a positive attitude toward breastfeeding were likely to exclusively breastfeed their infants. This result is supported by the American Medical Association (2008) which pointed out that most of the mothers perceived that breastfeeding promotes sensory and cognitive development, and protects the infants against infections and chronic diseases. Exclusive breastfeeding reduces infant mortality due to common childhood illness such as diarrhea or pneumonia and helps for a quicker recovering during illness. This result is supported by UNICEF (2008) who have enumerated the benefits of exclusive breastfeeding to include reduction of infant mortality rate, promotion of the health of all women and their role in the community and also promotes development in the children that grow health and productive leaders of tomorrow.

Test of the hypothesis: There is no significant relationship between the attitudes of career mothers and exclusive breastfeeding practice. Table 3 shows the result of the hypothesis tested.

Table 3: Pearson Product Moment Correlation (PPMC) showing the relationship between the attitudes of career mothers and exclusive breastfeeding practice

Variables	Mean	Std. Dev.	N	R	p-value	Remarks
Attitude of career mothers	16.5284	1.80769	176	.687*	.001	Sig.
Exclusive breastfeeding practices	18.9261	4.74735				

* Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

Table 3 presents the findings of a Pearson Product Moment Correlation (PPMC) analysis investigating the relationship between attitudes of career mothers and exclusive breastfeeding practice. The table showed that there is a statistical significant relationship between the attitudes of career mothers and exclusive breastfeeding practice ($r=.687$, $n=176$, $p (.001) <.05$). Hence, attitude of career mothers towards exclusive breastfeeding influenced/enhanced exclusive breastfeeding practices among career mothers in the study. The hypothesis is rejected.

CONCLUSION

The summary of the findings of this study showed that the respondents (career mothers) had a positive perception of exclusive breastfeeding and its inherent benefits. Similarly, they had positive attitude towards exclusive breastfeeding practice. Lastly, the relationship between the attitudes of career mother had significant impact on exclusive breastfeeding practice at 0.05 level of significance. Based on the findings of the study, it was concluded that career mothers in university of Ibadan and university college hospital were more aware of the importance of exclusive breastfeeding practice and the benefit derived from it. This study found that respondents had a good knowledge of EBF practice and a positive attitude toward it. Nearly all the respondents

started breastfeeding their babies within 24 hours of delivery, and they gave colostrum to the babies. This study also confirmed a significant link between respondents' knowledge, attitudes, perception and practices regarding maternal EBF.

The results of this study are critically important, that as they are addressing the gap in the EBF segment and sensitively show evidence for areas where urgent interventions are needed. However only, very few of them did posed negative attitude regarding tight schedule while majority of the nursing mother had positive perceptions regarding exclusive breast feeding. Thus career mothers should be advice to adopt exclusive breastfeeding as the best method of feeding their babies for the first six month of life. Also working class mothers in university of Ibadan and university college hospital should be educated on the benefits of exclusive breastfeeding to change their negative perception.

RECOMMENDATIONS

The following recommendations were put forward to improve the practice of exclusive breastfeeding among career mothers irrespective of the organisations where they work:

- In order to enhance exclusive breastfeeding practices, health workers should intensify their health talks, house visits and communication promoting breastfeeding.
- Career mothers should be informed of the risks and negative effects of improper newborn feeding techniques.
- Breastfeeding anti-discrimination laws should be established to solve the issue of discrimination against career mothers who wish to breastfeed in the workplace. This will ensure that career mothers will not shy away from breastfeeding in the public domain.
- Maternity leave should also be extended to allow the new mothers to have more time with the babies and to enhance exclusive breastfeeding for the recommended six months.
- Creches should be made available in offices to enable career mother's breastfeed their babies properly and teaching of mother's ways of expressing of breast milk and storage of expressed breast milk so as to improve the rate of exclusive breastfeeding practice by working mothers and the society at large.

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